

Problems and Barriers Militating against the Application of Paulo Freire's Pedagogy for Teaching and Learning in Bayelsa State Secondary Schools

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Abstract

Nigeria follows a 6-3-3-4 education system, comprising six years of primary schooling, three years of junior secondary education, three years of senior secondary education, and approximately four years of university or other tertiary education. This paper focuses on the teaching–learning processes within the 3-3 secondary education system, highlighting the persistence of traditional, teacher-centred methods and the limited engagement with the alternative pedagogical approach proposed by Paulo Freire, the renowned Brazilian educator and philosopher. The study further examines the challenges associated with adopting Freire's problem-posing and dialogic pedagogy at the secondary school level in Bayelsa State, reflecting broader systemic issues in secondary education across Nigeria, including Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory. Through a review of existing literature and interviews with selected secondary school teachers, several barriers were identified: lapses in school administration, constraints in curriculum implementation, insufficient time to cover extensive syllabi, large class sizes, pressures from internal and external examinations, teacher-related factors, deficiencies in pre-service teacher training, and limited access to professional development opportunities. The paper recommends that the government and relevant educational stakeholders address these challenges to facilitate the adoption of Freirean pedagogy, thereby enhancing the quality of teaching and learning in Bayelsa State and across Nigeria.

Keywords: *Problems, barriers, Paulo Freire's pedagogy, teaching and learning, Bayelsa State Secondary Schools.*

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Introduction

One major challenge associated with learning processes particularly within the Nigerian educational setting is the belief held by some teachers that learners are entirely devoid of prior knowledge. Such teachers tend to perceive learners as blank, passive

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containers awaiting content. As a result, the learning process becomes reduced to a mere act of depositing information, where learners serve as receivers and teachers function solely as depositors, much like rainwater being channelled into empty vessels. This situation reflects what is known as the Banking Concept of Education, which contradicts the true purpose of education as an inquiry-driven process in which learners explore knowledge under the guidance and direction of a teacher.

The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014), assert that the aim of education is to develop the creative abilities and competencies of individuals to ensure self-actualization and contribute to the overall advancement of society. This position implicitly acknowledges the inherent capacities that learners already possess capacities that the banking model fails to recognize. Consequently, there is a need for an alternative instructional approach that can correct this imbalance, one capable of empowering learners to participate meaningfully in the teaching-learning process and enhancing the quality of education delivered in secondary schools. Paulo Freire's model, as articulated in *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*, provides such an approach.

In this paper, Paulo Freire's pedagogy is interpreted as a method or model of teaching and learning grounded in teacher-pupil dialogue the dialogic, problem-posing, and problem-solving approach. Here, the teacher or pedagogue leads a group of learners through the teaching-learning process, acting as the team leader in classroom dialogue. The purpose of this paper is to give a brief overview of Freire's pedagogical ideas and to examine in detail the factors and challenges that have hindered its adoption by secondary schools in Bayelsa State and, by implication, in other regions of Nigeria.

Teaching and Learning Practices in Brazil and Nigeria Prior to Paulo Freire

Before Paulo Freire's intervention, the teaching-learning process in both Brazil and Nigeria followed similar patterns. In both contexts, traditional instructional methods dominated educational practice. These methods included the lecture method, talk-and-chalk, dictation, note-giving and note-taking, and the reading-round-the-class approach. Except for the reading-round-the-class method, all others positioned the teacher as the central figure active, in total control, and solely responsible for the flow of knowledge. Learners played a passive role, restricted mainly to copying notes dictated by the teacher, memorizing them, and reproducing the same information during examinations. Thus, the traditional teaching practice was overwhelmingly teacher-centred (Adeyinka, 2014).

It is against this pedagogical background that the present paper examines the nature of pre-Freirean teaching methods, Freire's call for an alternative pedagogy, the global embrace of Freirean principles, the persistence of the traditional approach in Nigeria, and the challenges that hinder the effective use of the Freirean teaching model in secondary schools in Bayelsa State and in Nigeria at large.

Paulo Freire: His Life and Work

Paulo Freire was born in Recife, Brazil, in 1921. His early encounters with poverty, despite living in a society with vast resources, significantly shaped his beliefs and writings on pedagogy and classroom practices (Freire, 1970). His awareness of Portugal's colonial influence on Brazil's indigenous people also fuelled his passion for

liberation and empowering the oppressed through education. Freire acknowledged that his teachers played a key role in shaping his philosophy of teaching. For instance, he recalled that his first teacher, Eunice Vasconcelos, constantly encouraged him to reflect critically and never treated him as a mere vessel to be filled (Freire, 1996: 29). In contrast, Freire's later experiences with formal schooling involved rote memorization and recitation of facts methods he often struggled with.

Growing up in Brazil enabled Freire to witness firsthand the divide between the wealthy and the poor through the experiences of his classmates (Freire, 1996). His mother's determination and support played a crucial role in helping him secure a scholarship to a private high school, even though the family lacked the financial means to afford such an institution. During this period, Freire personally experienced hunger which starkly contrasted with the comfort enjoyed by his classmates from privileged backgrounds. His high school years therefore deepened his understanding of social inequality and its implications for human development (Kirylo, 2011).

While still in high school, Freire developed a passion for learning through the support of a Portuguese tutor, eventually leading him to accept a teaching position at the same school after graduation. He rejected instructional methods based on memorization and recitation for evaluating students' abilities, preferring an approach that encouraged active teacher learner engagement. His techniques became well received by the school's administrators and teachers, and he was frequently invited to present his pedagogical ideas to colleagues (Kirylo, 2011).

During his teaching career, Freire experienced several promotions. However, political unrest in Brazil led to his arrest along with other members of the national education association. In April 1964, the military accused him of inciting dissatisfaction among ordinary citizens and encouraging political instability, which they believed threatened the interests of the elite. Though later released, he was subsequently exiled from Brazil (Schugurensky, 2011). After leaving Brazil, Freire briefly stayed in Bolivia before moving to the University of Chile, where he worked extensively with peasants. There, he developed the concept of "cultural circles," where he spent long sessions listening to the concerns of oppressed communities (Wallerstein, 1987). These experiences deepened his understanding of how education could be used as a tool for liberation, ultimately leading to the writing and publication of *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*, based on his interactions with people in Brazil and Chile.

Following the publication of the book, Freire's ideas quickly gained global attention. He received several invitations, including an appointment at Harvard University in the United States. During his time there, he further refined and disseminated his ideas on dialogic, problem-posing, and participatory models of teaching and learning (Freire 1996).

Paulo Freire's Critique of the Teaching/Learning Process in Brazilian Secondary Schools

Paulo Freire openly challenged the traditional instructional approach used in Brazilian secondary schools, arguing that it was excessively teacher-dominated and therefore ineffective for genuine learning. In essence, he dismissed the prevailing banking concept of education that shaped Brazilian schooling during his formative years. This form of pedagogy elevated the teacher's authority while pushing learners into a passive, subordinate role. Under such circumstances, students functioned as little more than

automatons, unable to generate their own ideas or engage meaningfully in the construction of knowledge (Adeyinka, 2014).

Paulo Freire's Advocacy of an Alternative Pedagogy

In response to these limitations, Paulo Freire proposed an alternative instructional model a critical pedagogy designed to minimize, or entirely remove, the overpowering influence of the teacher while transforming learners from passive recipients into active participants in the teaching-learning process. This method is built on dialogue, problem-posing, and problem-solving interactions (Yi-Huang, 2018). According to Yi-Huang, Freire, as a Brazilian educator, came to be regarded as a leading theorist of critical pedagogy whose ideas hold significant relevance for contemporary education across the globe.

Yi-Huang's work aims to re-examine Freire's dialogic pedagogy and clarify its implications for teaching practice. To achieve this, he first highlights the importance of Freire's emphasis on dialogue, and then considers both the theory and actual practice of dialogic engagement. He further demonstrates how teacher-student dialogue serves as a pathway for nurturing critical consciousness, and finally, he discusses the broader implications of dialogic pedagogy for classroom practice.

Drawing on related literature, Yi-Huang's analysis may be summarized as follows: the practice of love-centered teaching; the cultivation of humility-driven instruction; the nurturing of hope-based pedagogy; the integration of humor into learning; the deliberate promotion of students' critical thinking abilities; and the teacher's belief in learners' capacity to perform better when they participate actively in creating knowledge. Consequently, Freire's model has evolved into a widely recognized and influential new method of teaching.

Global Adoption of Paulo Freire's Pedagogy

Existing literature demonstrates the widespread international acceptance of Freire's pedagogical principles. Brown (2005) observes that Freire's global influence on education is profound. Many scholars regard him as "*the most influential educational philosopher in the development of critical pedagogical thought and practice*" (Darder et al., 2009). Recognizing his intellectual contribution, Kirylo (2011) described Freire as one of the foremost thinkers of his era, while Flannegan (2006) named him among "*the greatest educators ever.*" Freire's ideas have touched countless individuals, institutions, and nations across the world. According to Kirylo (2011), Freire's impact past and present extends to millions globally. Cornel West (1993) even referred to him as the "*exemplary organic intellectual of our time.*" Brown (2005) similarly asserted that Freire's internationally acclaimed work had transformed education at all levels.

Freire's pedagogy has been recognized and adopted in numerous developed countries across Europe, the Americas, and Asia, as well as in parts of the developing world, notably South Africa. A clear example is the establishment of the Freire Charter School (FCS) in Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, founded on Freire's problem-posing/problem-solving philosophy. The school's mission is to provide a college-preparatory education anchored in personal freedom, critical thinking, problem solving, and values such as teamwork, community, and non-violence (FCS, 2012). In practice, the school has earned a reputation for high academic performance and was named one of three high

schools in the United States to receive the Effective Practice Incentive Community (EPIC) award for improving academic achievement (Freire Charter School, n.d.).

Even after Freire's death in 1997, his influence continued to shape educational theory and practice worldwide (Allman, 2010). His legacy is also evident in institutions such as UCLA's Paulo Freire Institute and "The Freire Project" (Kincheloe, 2012), founded to build "an international critical community" dedicated to advancing social justice across cultures (Kincheloe, n.d.). Furthermore, a study by Steiner and Rozen (2004) found that *Pedagogy of the Oppressed* was the most frequently assigned text in philosophy of education courses across 16 American schools of education. Freire's ideas have also informed scholarly research in a variety of academic disciplines.

Perpetuation of the Status Quo in Nigeria/Bayelsa State

In contrast to the rapid global acceptance of Freire's alternative pedagogy, Nigeria continued to uphold the traditional approach to teaching. The teaching-learning system in Bayelsa State mirrored that of the broader Nigerian context. Teachers persisted in using conventional methods, lecture, talk-and-chalk, dictation, and reading-round-the-class while the teacher remained the central authority in the instructional process (Agih, 2021).

The persistence of the traditional pedagogy in Bayelsa State does not imply that teachers were unaware of Freire's model or its potential benefits. Rather, educators in Bayelsa, like their counterparts elsewhere in Nigeria, were unable to adopt the new approach due to numerous constraints. These challenges identified from literature and teacher feedback are outlined and discussed below.

Barriers to Implementing Paulo Freire's Pedagogy in Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State

As part of a broader investigation into Paulo Freire's *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*, relevant literature was reviewed, and thirty-six teachers drawn from thirty-six secondary schools in Bayelsa State were asked to identify the factors hindering the adoption of Freire's dialogic, problem-posing and problem-solving pedagogy at the secondary school level. The categories of challenges highlighted included: lapses in school administration; constraints in curriculum implementation; insufficient teaching time; large class sizes; pressures from internal and external examinations; teacher-related factors; continued reliance on the banking method of teaching; gaps in pre-service teacher preparation; and limited opportunities for professional development. These issues are discussed in the subsections below.

Lapses in School Administration

Participants reported that administrative practices both at the school level and within the state and federal education systems often function as impediments to the implementation of progressive pedagogies such as Freire's problem-posing/problem-solving model. From the outset, several teachers expressed the need for assurance that Ministry of Education officials were aware of the study and supportive of integrating Freirean methods into the school system. They argued that constant changes in teacher evaluation procedures suppress innovation and discourage creativity in classroom practice. Teachers also emphasized that administrators should allow them to remain in

a school long enough to make meaningful contributions to teaching and learning prior to being transferred.

Within the discussions on evaluation practices, Sika observed that “most teachers always resort back to their comfort zone, which Paulo Freire would label as banking, when it is time for teacher observation.” In response, the teachers proposed a more differentiated approach to evaluation, one that recognises differences in years of experience, past performance, student feedback, parental input, and overall effectiveness (Agih, 2018). A central requirement for enabling teachers to view administrators as partners rather than barriers is the cultivation of trust (Bottery, 2004). Busher (2006) stressed the importance of developing trust through collaboration between new and experienced mid-level administrators, working jointly to build a school climate that encourages innovation and change. Establishing a school culture that nurtures creativity and experimentation requires time and a deliberate commitment from school leaders to support teachers in the teaching and learning process.

Curriculum Implementation Issues

Another major barrier identified by teacher-respondents was the bulky, standards-driven, and examination-oriented curriculum. Participants stated that although they were excluded from the development of the secondary school curriculum in Bayelsa State, they were still required to implement it exactly as prescribed. They noted that frequent curriculum revisions particularly those involving continuous assessments reduced the opportunities for incorporating problem-posing instructional approaches. Many agreed that the strict standards limited their creativity as instructors.

Respondents also expressed the need for a unified curriculum that clearly outlines content and instructional timing. They argued that such structure would prevent a situation where teachers teach what they want, when they want, without common guidance. As emphasized that the curriculum should be more teacher-friendly, with weekly content guidelines that are realistic and manageable for both teachers and learners. Furthermore, the teacher-interviewees observed that many educators mistakenly equate curriculum solely with the subject content of various school subjects. Brown and Knowles (2007) cautioned that educators must adopt a broader understanding of curriculum, one that recognizes the entire school experience rather than limiting curriculum to textbook content. A shared understanding of curriculum would enable teachers to create experiences that align with the developmental needs of young adolescents. Accordingly, the curriculum must address not only content but also instructional objectives, teaching methods, and assessment strategies to ensure comprehensive learning.

Teachers also highlighted the need to integrate subject areas to help students perceive the relevance and interconnectedness of school learning. Curriculum experts continue to advocate integrated curricula that link classroom learning with real-world contexts. Interdisciplinary courses such as humanities replacing the traditional separation between language arts and social studies should be explored. According to Jackson and Davis (2000), curriculum must be relevant, challenging, integrative, and exploratory. A fragmented, subject-bound curriculum designed around adult interests cannot meet the demands of contemporary society. As Brown and Knowles (2007:75) stated:

In a world that can often seem contradictory and perplexing, such a curriculum offers minimal opportunities for student input and fails to provide the challenging and integrative experiences that most effectively engage learners. Textbooks seldom encourage exploration of concepts or the

drawing of meaningful connections; instead, they often reinforce existing social norms and predominantly reflect a White, male, European perspective. Consequently, the relevance students seek, the intellectual challenge they desire, and the connections they need are largely absent. Conversely, when students are immersed in a curriculum that is relevant, demanding, integrative, and exploratory, they are more likely to develop critical thinking skills and engage deeply with the learning process.

A significant barrier to implementing a more integrated and relevant curriculum is a self-imposed constraint, partially rooted in public expectations regarding input and output in public education. While the public rightly expects schools to provide students with new knowledge and skills daily, standards should serve merely as minimum benchmarks. A standards-based curriculum should be regarded as a guide for student learning rather than a rigid framework. Teachers' perceptions of curriculum inflexibility often hinder the consistent application of problem-posing strategies throughout the school day. Nonetheless, the pedagogical freedom enjoyed by many teachers provides opportunities to overcome the constraints posed by a seemingly rigid curriculum.

Limited Time to Cover Wide Subject Syllabi

Time limitations emerged as a major barrier to the application of Paulo Freire's pedagogy in Bayelsa State secondary schools, reflecting a broader challenge across Nigeria. Many teachers reported that they could not fully employ the Freirean method due to the restricted time available to cover extensive subject syllabi. Interviewees such as Ekanem, Kemi, Ebipre, and Kayode emphasised that frequent public holidays, strikes, and unscheduled school activities often left teachers feeling "one step behind." Consequently, teachers resorted to the traditional lecture method to ensure the syllabus was completed (Agih, 2021).

Teacher Characteristics

Bayelsa State secondary schools are staffed by teachers with diverse qualifications and experiences, including graduate and non-graduate teachers, trained and untrained teachers, and educators who may know the content but lack effective teaching strategies, or vice versa. These disparities compromise instructional effectiveness. Ideally, all teachers should possess both sound subject knowledge and proficient teaching techniques. At the junior secondary level, the minimum qualification should be the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE), while at the senior secondary level, most teachers should be trained graduates, equipped with knowledge and skills for integrating the latest technology. This expectation presupposes that school owners provide essential resources, such as computers and other instructional gadgets, to facilitate the teaching-learning process.

Continued Use of the 'Banking' Method of Teaching

A persistent barrier to adopting the problem-posing/problem-solving pedagogy is the continued reliance on the 'banking' method of teaching. In this approach, the teacher is assumed to possess complete knowledge, while learners are presumed to be blank vessels. The teacher transmits information en bloc, and students receive it passively, focusing primarily on passing internal and external examinations. This approach leaves no time for addressing individual learner needs or for engaging students in meaningful dialogues that encourage problem-solving (Adeyinka, 2014).

Lapses in Pre-service Training of Teachers

Participants highlighted deficiencies in pre-service teacher training as a barrier to implementing Freirean pedagogy. Pre-service training should provide the philosophical foundation of problem-posing pedagogy as well as practical teaching skills. Jackson and Davis (2000) emphasized the need for specialised pre-service training for middle-level educators. Interviewees such as Ekanem, Ufuoma, and Tamunoseki noted that successive Nigerian governments have neglected teacher welfare and professional preparation. Additionally, the current teaching practice period in Nigeria approximately twelve weeks across the last two academic years is significantly shorter than in developed countries, where trainee teachers may undergo a full academic year of practice, as at Northampton University in the UK (Adeyinka & Paulley, 2019). Exposure to traditional teaching methods in host schools often reinforces reliance on outdated pedagogies, which teachers are likely to continue using once they assume substantive roles (Agih, 2021).

Limited Opportunities for Teacher Professional Development

The interviewees also emphasized the scarcity of professional development opportunities. Professional development in Bayelsa schools as narrowly focused on improving standardized test scores. In contrast, Wilcox and Angelis (2009) argued that high-performing schools cultivate an environment conducive to high-quality, reflective professional development. Effective professional development should enhance pedagogy, as teaching and learning are central to secondary school success. Areas for professional development include the procurement and use of appropriate teaching aids and modern instructional technologies. Such initiatives are typically discussed at professional conferences, seminars, symposia, and summits, but teachers in Bayelsa State, like their counterparts in other Nigerian states, have limited access to these opportunities (Agih, 2021).

Conclusion

There exists a widespread assumption among teachers that learners enter the classroom as empty vessels, and it is the teachers' responsibility to fill this void with the knowledge necessary for passing internal and external examinations. As a result, learners are consistently excluded from the process of knowledge creation. Teachers typically provide notes for students to copy, which are later regurgitated during examinations. This traditional, teacher-centred approach to instruction was common in Brazil, Nigeria, and other countries before the emergence of Paulo Freire, the renowned Brazilian philosopher and educator. Freire rejected this conventional 'banking' method of teaching and advocated a participatory pedagogy, emphasizing dialogue, problem-posing, and problem-solving, which encourages active engagement by both teachers and learners. While many developed countries in Europe, North America, and Asia, as well as South Africa, have embraced the Freirean pedagogy, Nigeria, like many developing nations, has largely maintained the traditional status quo.

As revealed in the literature and corroborated by interviews with selected teachers, several factors continue to impede the adoption of Freire's pedagogy in Bayelsa State, mirroring challenges across other Nigerian states. These include lapses in school administration; a bulky, examination-oriented curriculum; limited instructional time; large class sizes of 50–60 pupils; inadequate instructional resources, including computers and other technologies; variability in teacher experience and qualifications;

insufficient pre-service training; and limited opportunities for ongoing professional development. Despite these challenges, there is strong belief that the Freirean pedagogy can be successfully implemented in Bayelsa State secondary schools and in other Nigerian states if educational authorities, school administrators, and teachers collectively address these barriers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to facilitate the effective adoption of Freire's pedagogy in Bayelsa State secondary schools:

1. School leaders at all levels should be trained to support innovative pedagogical approaches and create a climate that encourages teacher creativity and student participation.
2. The secondary school curriculum should be streamlined, teacher-friendly, and flexible, allowing opportunities for problem-posing and participatory learning.
3. Schools should ensure sufficient time allocation to cover syllabi while accommodating participatory and dialogic teaching methods.
4. Efforts should be made to reduce large class sizes to facilitate meaningful teacher-learner interactions.
5. Educational authorities should supply necessary teaching aids, including computers and modern technologies, to support effective pedagogy.
6. Schools should provide ongoing professional development opportunities that focus on pedagogy, curriculum integration, and the use of modern instructional tools.

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